

Effect of D-allulose on di-n-butyl phthalate (DBP) toxicity in rats

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Abstract

Background: Oral exposure to high concentrations of di-n-butyl phthalate (DBP) causes testicular and hepatotoxicity in rodents. DBP-metabolite, mono-n-butyl phthalate (MBP) stimulates peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors and disrupts carbohydrate and lipid metabolism. The oxidative stress generated may be closely related to these toxicities.

Method: To determine the effect of D-allulose on DBP-induced testicular and hepatotoxicity, rats were fed a DBP (1% or 2%) diet and D-allulose (2%) in the drinking water.

Result: Dietary exposure to DBP induced a significant decrease in testicular weight and significant increase in liver weight. D-allulose treatment slightly inhibited the testicular weight loss, but did not suppress the increase in liver weight. Plasma TCH and HDL-C were significantly reduced in the DBP alone group compared with the control group, and slightly improved by D-allulose administration, but not significantly. Plasma glucose levels were significantly reduced in the DBP alone group compared with the control group. Multiple regression analysis of the effect of D-allulose administration on plasma glucose levels in the DBP-administered group suggested that D-allulose administration could suppress the decrease in plasma glucose levels caused by DBP. D-allulose may regulate excessive insulin secretion.

Conclusion: D-allulose was found to reduce testicular and hepatotoxicity induced by DBP in rats. This effect is thought to be due to the strong oxidant scavenging ability of D-allulose.

Keywords: D-Allulose; DBP; testicular toxicity; hepatotoxicity; oxidative stress.

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1. Introduction

Dibutyl phthalate (DBP) is an organic compound that is widely used as a plasticizer and also as an additive in adhesives and printing inks. Oral administration of high concentrations of DBP causes testicular and hepatotoxicity in rodents [1-5] Phthalate metabolite, mono-n-butyl phthalate (MBP) stimulates peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors and disrupts carbohydrate and lipid metabolism [6, 7]. There appears to be a close relationship between the occurrence of oxidative stress and these toxicities. In this study shows the effect of the rare sugar D-allulose, which has strong radical scavenging ability [8, 9], on testicular and hepatotoxicity induced by DBP.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and Animal Diet

Chemical purity > 97% DBP were purchased from Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd. (Osaka, Japan). The CE-2 diets (Clea, Tokyo, Japan) containing DBP were prepared by Oriental Yeast Company (Chiba, Japan). D-allulose was provided by Kagawa Rare Sugar Research Center (Kagawa, Japan). The chemical purity of D-allulose was found to be >98%.

2.2. Animals and Ethics

Male Sprague-Dawley rats aged three-week-old purchased from Charles River (Kanagawa, Japan) were housed at the Laboratory Animal Center of Kagawa University. They were acclimated at 22–24 °C and 50–60% relative humidity with a 12-h light/dark cycle. The experiment protocols had the approval by the Kagawa University Animal Committee.

2.3. Experimental Design

In the first experiment, four-week-old rats weighing (84.9 ± 2.9 g) were divided into control and treatment groups consisting of 6 animals. The treatment group consumed 1% (w / w) DBP diet and sugar free water (tap water) or 2% (w / w) D-allulose water for two weeks. At the end of the experiment, rats were sacrificed by ether anesthesia. The testis and liver were removed and weighed. Blood samples collected from the heart were collected into heparinized tubes and plasma was separated from whole blood by centrifugation at 1500 g and plasma were frozen at -40 °C until biochemical parameter measurement.

In the second experiment, four-week-old rats weighing (102.5 ± 4.2 g) were divided into control and treatment groups consisting of 6 animals. The treatment group consumed 2% (w / w) DBP diet and sugar free water (tap water) or 2% (w / w) D-allulose water for two weeks. At the end of the experiment, rats

were sacrificed by ether anesthesia. The testis and liver were removed and weighed. Blood samples collected from the heart were collected into heparinized tubes and plasma was separated from whole blood by centrifugation at 1500 g and plasma were frozen at -40 ° C until biochemical parameter measurement.

2.4. Plasma Biochemical Parameter Measurements

Plasma levels of glucose, total cholesterol, high density lipoprotein cholesterol and triglyceride were measured using an automated biochemical analyzer, Hitachi 7600 (Hitachi, Japan).

2.5. Statistical Analysis

The results are shown as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was performed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Dunnett's test for multiple comparisons. In addition, multiple regression analysis was performed to clarify the effect of D-allulose administration on plasma glucose levels. $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. First experiment

Table 1 shows body weight, organ weights and relative organ weights of rats treated with 1% (w/w) DBP diet and sugar-free water or 2% (w/w) D-allulose water for 2 weeks. The DBP group showed a significant increase in liver weight compared to the Control group. On the other hand, testis weight significantly decreased in the DBP alone group, but not in the D-allulose group.

Table 2 shows the plasma biochemical parameters of rats treated with the DBP diet and either sugar-free water or 2% (w/w) D-allulose water for 2 weeks. Plasma glucose concentrations were significantly lower in the DBP alone group than in the control group, but not in the D-allulose group. Plasma lipid-related markers such as total cholesterol (TCH) and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) were significantly lower in all DBP diet groups than in controls and slightly improved by D-allulose administration, but not significantly.

3.2. Second experiment

Table 3 shows body weight, organ weights and relative organ weights of rats treated with 2% (w/w) DBP diet and sugar-free water or 2% (w/w) D-allulose water for 2 weeks. The DBP group showed a significant increase in liver weight compared to the Control group. On the other hand, testis weight decreased significantly in the DBP alone group and the DBP + D-allulose group, but the decrease was less in the DBP

+ D-allulose group.

Table 1. Body and organ weights, relative organ weights (as a percentage of body weight) of the rats treated with 1% (w / w) DBPdiet plus sugar-free water or 2% (w / w) D-allulose water for two weeks. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001as compared to Control. #p < 0.05, ##p < 0.01, ###p < 0.001 as compared to 1% DBP alone.

Group	Control	1%DBP	1%DBP+2%Allulose
n	6	6	6
Initial body weight (g)	85.0 ± 2.8	84.8 ± 2.8	84.8 ± 3.8
Final body weight (g)	193.8 ± 9.1	199.8 ± 5.6	192 ± 8.2
Testes (g)	1.87 ± 0.25 #	1.47 ± 0.35 *	1.67 ± 0.09
Relative testicular weight (%)	0.97 ± 0.14 #	0.73 ± 0.18 *	0.87 ± 0.05
Liver (g)	9.26 ± 1.19 ###	12.59 ± 0.73 ***	12.17 ± 1.2 **
Relative liver weight (%)	4.81 ± 0.81 ###	6.30 ± 0.30 ***	6.33 ± 0.36 ***

Table 2. Plasma Biochemical Parameters of the rats treated with 1% (w / w) DBP diet plus sugar-free water or 2% (w / w) D-allulose water for two weeks. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001as compared to Control. #p < 0.05, ##p < 0.01, ###p < 0.001as compared to 1%DBP alone.

Group	Control	1%DBP	1%DBP+2%Allulose
n	6	6	6
Glucose (mg/dL)	188.3 ± 51.9 #	73.3 ± 36.0 *	161 ± 100.6
TC (mg/dL)	86.8 ± 11.5 ##	66 ± 5.7 **	71.7 ± 4.3 **
HDL-C (mg/dL)	41.7 ± 4.3 ###	29.8 ± 3.1 ***	31.7 ± 1.2 ***
TG (mg/dL)	35.3 ± 12.5	28.7 ± 11.3	28.0 ± 11.7

Table 3. Body and organ weights, relative organ weights (as a percentage of body weight) of the rats treated with 2% (w / w) DBPdiet plus sugar-free water or 2% (w / w) D-allulose water for two weeks. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001as compared to Control. #p < 0.05, ##p < 0.01, ###p < 0.001 as compared to 1% DBP alone.

Group	Control	2%DBP	2%DBP+2%Allulose
n	6	6	6
Initial body weight (g)	105.3 ± 1.9	99.8 ± 5.5	102.3 ± 2.9
Final body weight (g)	226.7 ± 12.6 ##	197.8 ± 10.4 **	168.2 ± 18.8 ***
Testes (g)	1.98 ± 0.11 ###	0.74 ± 0.05 ***	0.81 ± 0.16 ***
Relative testicular weight (%)	0.88 ± 0.08 ###	0.38 ± 0.04 ***	0.49 ± 0.09 ***
Liver (g)	10.8 ± 1.0 ##	13.7 ± 1.0 **	10.9 ± 1.7
Relative liver weight (%)	4.77 ± 0.38 ###	6.94 ± 0.18 ***	6.49 ± 0.54 ***

Table 4. Plasma Biochemical Parameters of the rats treated with 2% (w / w) DBP diet plus sugar-free water or 2% (w / w) D-allulose water for two weeks. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 as compared to Control. #p < 0.05, ##p < 0.01, ###p < 0.001 as compared to 1%DBP alone.

Group	Control	2%DBP	2%DBP+2%Allulose
n	6	6	6
Glucose (mg/dL)	221.8 ± 108.9 #	138.3 ± 73.1 *	174.7 ± 56.4
TC (mg/dL)	77.0 ± 6.6 ##	66.2 ± 6.0 **	77.2 ± 15.5 **
HDL-C (mg/dL)	33.5 ± 2.8 ###	29.3 ± 2.3 ***	31.2 ± 5.0 ***
TG (mg/dL)	107.2 ± 43.2 ##	46.2 ± 19.4 **	39.5 ± 7.7 **

Table 4 shows the plasma biochemical parameters of rats treated with the DBP diet and either sugar-free water or 2% (w/w) D-allulose water for 2 weeks. Plasma glucose concentrations were lower in the DBP alone and DBP+D-allulose groups than in the control group, but not significantly, and plasma glucose level was higher in the DBP+D-allulose group than in the DBP alone group. Plasma lipid-related markers such as TCH and HDL-C were significantly lower in DBP diet alone groups than in controls and slightly improved by D-allulose administration, but not significantly.

Table 5 shows the results of multiple regression analysis of the effect of D-allulose administration on plasma glucose levels in the DBP-treated groups, which indicates that D-allulose administration can prevent DBP from lowering plasma glucose levels.

Table 5. Multiple regression analysis with plasma glucose as the dependent variable and DBP treatment and D-allulose treatment as explanatory variables

	Estimated regression coefficient, B	Standard Error, S.E.	Partial regression coefficient, β	Partial R	P-value
Intercept	205.08	21.85	-	-	0.000
DBP	-99.25	30.91	-0.562	-0.488	0.003 **
D-allulose	0.191	0.101	0.351	0.335	0.050 *

Glucose (mg/dL) as the dependent variable, *significant at p<0.05, **significant at p<0.01.

4. Discussion

D-allulose (D-psicose), known as an artificial sweetener, is a monosaccharide that is about 70% as sweet as sucrose, but has 1/10 the calories of sucrose. It is also found in small amounts in figs, raisins, molasses, maple syrup, etc., and is also called a "rare sugar" in Japan due to its low content. D-allulose has been certified as GRAS (Generally Recognized as Safe) by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA). Since Ken Izumimori and others at Kagawa University established a mass production method for rare sugars using the enzymatic isomerization method [10-12], research has been conducted to clarify the

antioxidant and anti-apoptotic effects of rare sugars [13-15]. In particular, D-allulose is known to exhibit stronger radical scavenging activity than other monosaccharides [9, 16].

On the other hand, orally administered DBP is hydrolyzed by lipase to the monoester MBP [17-20]. MBP is known as a potent oxidative stress factor, and has been reported to inhibit the function of Sertoli cells, induce reproductive toxicity, and cause apoptosis of germ cells [21-23]. MBP is also known to be a PPAR agonist [24]. PPAR agonists induce peroxisome proliferation, causing hepatic hypertrophy [25, 26] and upregulation of glucose and lipid metabolism in rats [26-30].

In this study, dietary exposure to DBP caused a significant decrease in testis weight and a significant increase in liver weight. Administration of D-allulose slightly inhibited the decrease in testis weight. However, D-allulose did not significantly inhibit the increase in liver weight. Plasma TCH and HDL-C were significantly reduced in the DBP alone group compared with the control group, and slightly improved by D-allulose administration, but not significantly. Plasma glucose levels were significantly reduced in the DBP alone group compared with the control group. Multiple regression analysis of the effect of D-allulose administration on plasma glucose levels in the DBP-administered group suggested that D-allulose administration could suppress the decrease in plasma glucose levels caused by DBP. PPAR- γ induced by MBP promotes insulin secretion [29, 30]. Oxidative stress scavenging action of D-allulose may regulate excessive insulin secretion.

5. Conclusion

D-allulose was found to reduce testicular and hepatotoxicity induced by DBP in rats. This effect is thought to be due to the strong oxidant scavenging ability of D-allulose.

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this work.

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